

"FRACTIONAL NUMBERS AND ACTIONS ON THEM" IN THE V CLASSES OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS TECHNOLOGY OF ASSIMILATION OF MATERIALS ON THE SUBJECT

Ibrahimov F.

*Sheki branch of ADPU,
Doctor of pedagogical sciences, professor
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0775-1048>*

Suleymanova K.

*Teacher of the Department of Natural
Sciences and their Teaching Technology
of the Sheki branch of ADPU*

Abstract

In the article, the content of the skills intended to become the subject of students in the process of teaching materials on the subject of "Fractional numbers and operations on them", which is included in the content of the Mathematics subject in the V classes of general education schools, is presented. In the formation of the mentioned skills, attention is focused on the presence of content elements that carry the function of "opportunity" in the topic "Fractional numbers and actions on them" and the technology of turning them into actions in the students' cognition (adequate to the paradigm "movement-possibility-new quality"). "Fractional numbers and actions on them" based on the "system-structure" dialectical approach, the elements of which are transformed in the "deeds" topic "Divisors of the number"; "Fractions"; "Finding the part of a number and the number by the part"; "Addition and subtraction of fractions"; "Decimal fractions"; "Decimal fractions and floor prices"; "Comparison of Decimal Fractions"; "Rounding Decimals. Estimated sum, estimated difference"; "Addition and subtraction of decimal fractions"; "Multiplication of decimal fractions"; It is considered appropriate to turn it into a system for the subtopics of "Division of decimal fractions and division of decimal fractions". It should be noted that the system of assignments (questions, problems, work) that serves as a means of organizing and managing the educational process for mastering the content elements presented by the students should contain verbs that are required to be performed in the topics. Examples of such assignments are included in the content of the work.

Keywords: fraction; part of a number; ordinary and decimal fractions; approximate sum and difference; rounding; floor units; estimated price; dividers; training; teaching process; teaching unit; standard; substandard; system; "system-structure" approach; technology.

The actuality of the subject. There are no recommendations that are useful to be adopted for guidance in the teacher's activity in the currently used textbook set [7-8] and in various educational literature about the teaching units, basic standards, substandards, and teaching of certain subjects in the subject of mathematics. These are very useful in terms of teaching the process of teaching mathematics according to the curriculum model. It is not denied that continuous improvement of the teaching process in the subject is logical, most didactic problems are eternal. Of course, as the experience of using the curriculum is formed, the methodical system (technology) of the teaching process adequate to it should be improved. Based on this logic, we claim the relevance of the research on "Technology of assimilation of materials on the subject of "Fractional numbers and operations on them" in V classes of general education schools".

Interpretation of generalizations based on information obtained on the basis of research. In order to clarify the logic of the presented scientific interpretation, let us emphasize that in summarizing the materials obtained on the research topic, in addition to referring to the forms and methods of scientific cognition, "training and teaching activity", "learning and mastering", "content and content line", "expected main standard with result", "main standard and sub-standards", "system-whole-part-element relations" were focused [2].

Scientific sources indicate that "training" and "educational activity" are one of the main concepts of pedagogy. Although training is an important characteristic

of educational activity, it does not cover all aspects of it. Training, in the broadest sense of the word, involves the acquisition of new knowledge, skills and habits. However, learning and learning activities are essentially different events. Appropriation is an integral part not only of the learning process, but of every field of activity [1;150]. This scientific consideration was also taken into account when making the generalization.

The analysis of the materials obtained from scientific sources leads us to the conclusion that training is a way of implementing education, and the fact that spiritual learning, memorizing what has been learned, and acquiring the experience of creative activity based on it depends on the way of learning (the dialectic of the content and form of cognitive action)[11]. Forming a model of educational implementation in didactics is a perennial problem. [3] Therefore, special importance was given to creative and critical thinking while generalizing.

Based on the idea of L.Bertalanfi to get to the essence of many pedagogical concepts, to give an honest scientific interpretation, in our opinion, it is a successful approach, the "system-structural approach" is a branch of dialectics that has gained an independent "status" since the thirties of the 20th century [10; 8]. In the analysis of the obtained materials and the implementation of generalizations, the scientific method in question was accepted as a form of action.

The technology of education implementation (methodology in the traditional approach) has its own

system [5]. The expected result in the mentioned technological system is determined by the state of movement of the selected content. There should be a technological system suitable for each content line, teaching unit, subject. Since the authenticity of this opinion does not leave any room for doubt in us, in the content line "Numbers and actions" in class V, "Natural numbers. Number systems. The selection of an adequate system was brought into the center of attention in the design of the implementation technology of the content standards on the topic "Operations on multi-digit numbers". [7]

The teaching process of the subtopics covered in the topic "Fractional numbers and operations on them" is directed to the purpose of making students the subject of the following skills (mastering a certain part of the results expected in the teaching of the standards-subject): 1.2.1. Performs calculation operations on natural numbers; 1.2.2. Multiplies and divides natural numbers, decimal fractions by floor units; 1.2.4. Adds fractions and mixed numbers with the same denominator, performs calculations on resulting decimal fractions; 1.2.5. Finds the part of the number; 1.3.1. Rounds natural numbers and decimal fractions to the required level [6; 301-345].

During the teaching process of the sub-topic "Divisors of numbers", which is included in the topic "Fractional numbers and operations on them", students should have the opportunity (environment) to obtain general information as follows. They should know that the sum and product of two natural numbers is always a natural number. However, the difference of two natural numbers can be a natural number only if the decreasing number is greater than the subtracted one. At the same time, the quotient of two natural numbers is not always a natural number. For this, first of all, the divisor must be greater than or equal to the dividend, and the dividend must be completely divisible.

It should be clear to the students that when dividing one natural number by another, when a natural number is obtained as a quotient, the reasoning "the first number is exactly divisible by the second" can be said. happens.

All natural numbers are divisible both by themselves and by 1. That is, if a is a natural number, then it can be written that $a:1=a, a:a=1$.

Among the natural numbers, numbers greater than 1 that are divisible only by themselves and 1 occupy a special place. Such numbers are called simple (real) numbers. Students should be able to interpret the definition "A natural number divisible only by itself and 1 or with only two divisors is called a prime number" based on specific examples. It should be clear to them that since there are an infinite number of prime numbers, it is impossible to write them all. Thus, new prime numbers different from those numbers can be added to any sequence of prime numbers. Among the natural numbers, there are numbers that are divisible by other numbers in addition to the unit and itself, such numbers are also infinite. Students should be able to interpret the definition "A natural number with a divisor other than itself and unity is called a complex number", and should be able to distinguish between complex numbers: each complex number is divisible by itself, by 1, and by at least one natural number. Among the natural numbers,

1 is the only number that is neither prime nor complex. This number has only one divisor equal to itself. The set of natural numbers consists of prime numbers, complex numbers and the unit.

Students should have the necessary knowledge of "prime divisor". They should know that the natural number divided by the given natural number is called the divisor of that natural number. Students should conclude that if a is a prime number, it has two divisors: 1 and a . If b is a complex number, then this number has at least one divisor besides 1 and b . If the divisor is a prime number, then it is called a prime divisor.

A system of tasks is formed and implemented for students to make themselves the level of an active carrier of the above-mentioned information. In which the mentioned system of tasks should target the following student skills: 1) determine the divisors of the number according to the signs of division; 2) determines the divisors of a number by expressing it as the product of two multiplications; 3) solves various problems based on the divisors of the number.

In the course of the lesson, the teacher should make the above-mentioned generalizations, taking into account the results of the collective and group activities of the students on the tasks. It is advisable to carry out the evaluation on the basis of criteria adequate to the expected results (skills).

The teacher can start the first lesson focused on the teaching of the sub-topic "Fractions" with the students writing the fractions according to the "fraction cards" prepared in advance. This serves as a diagnostic assessment. For this purpose, worksheets are distributed to the class and students write the fractions according to the models within the specified time. The teacher checks the performance of the work and evaluates it through observation. Thus, the level of preparation for the subject of the class is determined.

Students should understand fractions as parts of a whole divided into equal parts. They should be able to compare fractions with the same denominators both on models and in mathematical writing. It is useful to bring to the students' attention that in daily life situations, there are more fractional numbers (ordinary fractions, decimal fractions, percentages) than natural numbers.

In this lesson, the following type of tasks can be preferred: 1) arranging fractions with the same denominators in ascending or descending order; 2) choose the fraction closest to the unit from the given fractions; 3) to separate the required number of items from a certain group of items.

In the further continuation of the teaching of the subject, equal fractions are examined on models. The correct sequence of manipulative, pictorial-mental, abstract stages of learning allows the student to learn the subject better. Students should know that fractions with the same numerator and denominator are equal to one. In other words, it should be clear to them that when you divide a number by itself, you get a unit.

Students should be able to reduce and simplify fractions. They should understand that it is possible to get (write) fractions by multiplying and dividing the numerator and denominator of a fraction by the same number. Students should know that for even fractions

there is only one non-reducible fraction, a simple fraction. It should be clear to them that any reducible fraction is taken and the equivalent fractions obtained by stepwise reduction are written on this fraction. Finally, such a fraction is obtained that it is no longer possible to reduce it. This fraction is called a simple fraction. In order to achieve the expected result, it is recommended to use tasks selected on scientific and pedagogical grounds:

It is possible to ensure that students work more actively in these classes. Because fractions are written on small numbers and there is no need for difficult calculations. These activities, which are based more on judgment and proof, linking skills, develop the student's logical and analytical thinking abilities. To simplify fractions, students should be regularly reminded that division signs are important.

Improper fractions and mixed numbers are one of the content elements that have an important place in the teaching of the subject. Improper fractions and mixed numbers are expressed in words and written based on the given models. The procedure for converting an improper fraction into a mixed number with the help of division is explained. This rule is explained to the students on life situations. In the teaching of the subject, the relationship between the dividing, divisor, and remainder components (elements of the fraction) is investigated as a whole class activity. It is necessary to explain to the students that the mixed number is one of the ways of writing the residual division. This is conditioned by the application of appropriate tasks.

One of the important issues is to investigate the relationship of mixed numbers over real situations and problems related to remainder division. The student should know the three spellings of fractions and be able to use them in his activities. The student should be able to think like this: if we look at the conversion of an improper fraction into a mixed number as the performance of division, then converting a mixed number into an improper fraction means finding the divisor. For this, the relationship between the divisor and the divisor, the quotient and the remainder can be used in the division with the remainder: $\text{divisor} = \text{divisor} \cdot \text{quotient} + \text{remainder}$

Comparing fractions is one of the important content elements in teaching the subject. Here, attention should be focused on three issues: 1) Comparison of fractions with equal denominators; 2) Comparison of fractions with equal copies; 3) Comparison of fractions with different numerators and denominators.

It is recommended to compare all three types of fractions first on fraction cards. The student can easily visually compare all three types of fractions on the fraction cards. Fraction estimation skills are important for building fraction comparison skills.

Whether students come to the conclusion that one of the ways to compare fractions is to equalize the denominators of fractions depends on the construction of the teaching process. Students must conclude that the fraction with the larger numerator is the larger of the two fractions with equal denominators. With the same approach, they should conclude that the fraction with the smaller denominator is larger than the fractions with equal denominators.

It is important to use the number axis when comparing fractions. The part corresponding to the unit on the number axis is divided into equal parts according to the denominator of the fraction. Fractions are placed on the number line both as improper fractions and as mixed numbers. Students learn the technology of using the number axis to compare fractions with specific examples.

In the teaching of the subject, information and tasks are selected based on the following "expected student skills": 1) Presents fractions in words and models; 2) presents a comparison of fractions with a model; 3) It presents the comparison of fractions in words and mathematical writing.

The assessment determines the level of students' mastery of the concepts of equal fractions, proper and improper fractions, and mixed numbers, the ability to compare and reduce fractions, and convert improper fractions to mixed numbers and vice versa.

The students started the preparation for the subtopic "Finding the part of the number and the number by the part" from the 4th grade. Despite this, many students find it difficult to solve problems related to finding a number. Experience shows that the use of the whole-part model eliminates the difficulties in mastering this subject by students. With the help of the whole-part model, it is possible to form the skills of solving problems based on fractions even in weak students. When selecting and systematizing the tasks to be applied in this lesson, the student skills presented below (targeted by topic) should be focused. These are the following: 1) presents the part of the number and by part with numerical models; 2) finds the part of the number and the number according to the part; 3) solves problems related to finding the part of the number and the number by the part. [9; 78]

According to our subjective understanding, the expected student skills in teaching the subtopic "Addition and Subtraction of Fractions" are: 1) adds and subtracts correct fractions with the same denominator; 2) Adds and subtracts improper fractions and mixed numbers with the same denominator; 3) It solves problems related to finding the number by its part and the part by the number.

Fraction addition and subtraction exercises are based on proper fractions, improper fractions, and mixed numbers with the same denominator. During the execution of these tasks, it is regularly kept in mind through observation that the student correctly understands the essence of the fraction. For example, the student must understand that in the fraction $1\frac{1}{4}$, each integer consists of 4 units of $\frac{1}{4}$. and there is $1\frac{1}{4}$.

In order for all students to visually understand the essence of fractions and operations on fractions, the processes of modeling whole numbers with "fraction cards" of different sizes are carried out. It should be clear to each student that he needs 4 such cards to model 1 whole with $\frac{1}{4}$ cards, and 8 such cards to model 2 wholes. Adding improper fractions and converting them to mixed numbers, their addition is again demonstrated on the cards.

In the teaching of the subject, it is recommended to include the following task examples: 1) addition of fractions with the same denominator; 2) collection of

fractions that can be reduced to the same denominator; addition of improper fractions with the same denominator; 3) addition of mixed numbers; finding the value of expressions given by fractions according to the order of operations (required to add a proper fraction, an improper fraction, and a mixed number with the same denominators); 4) finding a number by its part and issues related to finding a part by a number; 5) solving problems with the part-whole model.

It is recommended to solve even the simplest problems based on fractions with a model, so that students get used to modeling problems suitable for difficult situations.

If the procedure for adding opposite numbers is explained in the problem solving (based on the whole-part model), it will be better understood by the students. Approaching the problem from the mentioned aspect, it is possible to offer the students to solve such a problem: Javid and Rauf had the same amount of money. Javid spent 25 manats of his money, and Rauf spent 35 manats. Now Rauf's money is $\frac{4}{5}$ of Javid's money. How much money did each of them have at first?

Recommended types of tasks for subtraction of fractions with the same denominators may include: 1) subtraction of correct fractions with equal denominators; 2) relating to the subtraction of improper fractions with equal denominators; 3) related to the subtraction of mixed numbers with the same denominators; 4) relating to subtraction of the fraction from the whole; required to find the part by the number and the number by the part; 5) solved by the integral part model. [9; 81-82]

Solving problems based on fractions is very important for developing the student's problem solving skills in general. Since it is convenient to present these problems with models, the student visualizes the problem in his imagination and enters the situation of the problem. Students suffer when solving difficult problems based on fractions through questions and answers. However, modeling can easily solve many of these issues. It is recommended to perform the suggested exercises on fraction cards for students related to subtraction on fractions. When the student prepares fraction cards, he understands the essence of actions on such fractions. Therefore, it would be more appropriate to solve the problem on fractional numbers by building an "integer-part model".

Subtracting a fraction from an integer is a useful approach explained on models and numerical examples. Let's try to bring clarity to our reasoning in the example of working on an issue.

Problem: 9 of Shamkhal's balls went through the goal, 6 were caught by the goalkeeper, and 3 missed the goal. Compare the fraction corresponding to the number of goals scored by Shamkhal and the fraction corresponding to the number of balls caught by the goalkeeper.

Based on the performance of this task, a formative assessment can be made on the student's ability to understand the essence of fractions and express information with fractions. The student who has advanced to the level of the subject of the activity according to the situation of the problem understands that the ratio of the total number of goals scored to the number of

balls that go through the goal is the part of the goals that go through the goal, and it is written as a fraction, and it is more correct to express the part with a simple fraction.

The process of solving the problem is mainly based on the following nuances: The total number of events is determined to be $9+6+3=18$. Any of the students writes or presents the appropriate fractions orally. Other students report their relationship: $\frac{9}{18}=\frac{1}{2}$; $\frac{6}{18}=\frac{1}{3}$; $\frac{3}{18}=\frac{1}{6}$. We exchange ideas with the students as follows: We say that two-thirds of the balls hit went through the goal, one-third were caught by the goalkeeper, and one-sixth went past the goal. So, how do we express all branches as part?

Thus, students understand that all branches make up 1 whole. [9; 82]

In the lessons related to the teaching of the subject, the evaluation is carried out by levels based on the criteria. Here, it is advisable to consider three levels (can't perform, performs with partial difficulty, needs guidance from the teacher, performs freely and is able to apply it to solving problems).

Small summative assessment criteria: 1. Model proper fractions and improper fractions; 2. Presents the comparison of fractions with models and mathematical writings; 3. Adds and subtracts improper fractions and mixed numbers with equal denominators; 4. Solves problems related to finding the number by its part and the part by the number; 5. Presents data in the form of a circular diagram; 6. It solves problems by building a full-part model. [9; 84]

Teaching-methodical sources indicate that it is enough to allocate 2 hours of study to the sub-topic "Decimal Fractions". Thanks to the teaching of this topic, students should be able to: find denominators of 10, 100, 1000, etc. to write ordinary fractions as decimal fractions; modeling decimal fractions on a grid; to describe decimal fractions in an equivalent form (in a standard way, clearly - in the form of sum of floor values, in words, etc.); to solve problems based on floor values. [9; 88]

Experience shows that teaching both ordinary fractions and decimal fractions on models leads to ensuring the active participation of all students in the lesson. Therefore, pre-prepared decimal fraction cards are attached to the board. In this lesson, a 10×10 grid-100 square is a convenient tool for modeling decimal fractions. It is possible and useful to provoke students to think according to the purpose of the lesson on the basis of the mentioned network. It is made clear to the students by referring to the functions of visualization that the denominators of decimal fractions are 10, 100, 1000, etc. is the writing of ordinary fractions in a different form. The integer part of the decimal fraction is separated from the fractional part by a comma.

In the process of teaching the subject, the following points should be kept in focus: 1) It is appropriate to teach decimal fractions on models to children with poor learning ability; 2) Since the procedure for performing calculations on decimal fractions and natural numbers is similar, these lessons can be evaluated as a repeated opportunity to develop the skills of expression, calculation, and problem solving in equivalent numerical forms; 3) Decimal fractions modeling tasks on

checkered sheets develop students' research and information linking skills. It is recommended that all students be involved in the execution of tasks of this kind at the same time as a whole-class activity; 4) Tasks of writing and reading decimal fractions are performed. At this time, care should be taken to write decimal fractions in equivalent forms; 5) When performing the tasks, models corresponding to decimal fractions should be drawn, decimal fractions should be written according to the models; 6) Decimal fractions should be placed on the number axis. The decimal fraction corresponding to the point marked on the number axis should be determined. Tasks based on the skills of writing and reading decimal fractions, expressing mixed numbers with decimal fractions, recording decimal fractions on the number axis should be performed; 7) It should be taken into account that the tasks of placing decimal fractions on the number axis with a certain scale are important for the formation of students' calculation and information schematic representation skills. [6; 315]

Tasks should be systematized and applied to all classes and groups (through worksheets) according to the research question.

In the lesson, it is recommended to conduct a formative assessment through observation of the student's skills of models with ordinary and decimal fractions, expressing decimal fractions with models and ordinary fractions, reading and writing decimal fractions, placing decimal fractions on the number line. [8; 76-77]

It is enough to allocate 1 lesson hour to the teaching of the subtopic "Decimal fractions and floor values". Thanks to the teaching of this topic, students should be able to: determine the floor values of decimal fractions; to write decimal fractions as sums of floor values; to express decimal fractions in equivalent notations.

In the lesson, students' activities are organized on the table of floor prices prepared in advance. Together with the students, the floor units, their name and the value of the number are determined. Since the decimal fraction consists of whole and fractional parts, it is noted that the value of the numbers in each part is according to the floor location.

In the process of teaching the subject, the tasks of expressing decimal fractions with equivalent writings: in standard form with numbers, with the sum of the floor values of the numbers, in words, with the number of floor units are performed (Standard form: 14,123; In words: fourteen whole thousand one hundred and twenty-three; Open form - the sum of the floor values with: $10+4+0.1+0.02+0.003$ or $14T+1OB+2YB+3MB$ etc.).

The teaching process of the subject should be structured in such a way that the student has the opportunity to understand that the value of the number on each subsequent floor (from the comma to the right) in the fractional part is 10 times smaller than the value of the number on the previous floor.

It is recommended that the tasks be presented to the students in order to organize the work in groups.

During the lesson, formative evaluation can be conducted according to the activity of students and the level of performance of tasks.

It is enough to devote 1 lesson hour to teaching the sub-topic "Comparison of Decimal Fractions". Thanks to the teaching of this subject, students should be able to: 1) compare decimal fractions; 2) arrange decimal fractions according to increasing or decreasing order; 3) to present the comparison of decimal fractions on the number line.

It is recommended to start the lesson with a comparison of natural numbers. It is known to the students that the natural number with the larger number of digits is larger than two natural numbers with different numbers of digits.

The teacher poses a question to the students: "Can this rule be correct for decimal fractions?" For example: Can you say that 4.245 is greater than 17.3?" Students say their thoughts.

The generalization becomes:

1. Integer parts of decimal fractions are compared. The decimal fraction with more digits in the whole part is larger than two decimal fractions with different numbers of digits in the whole part. For example, $12.4 > 1.345$. 2. Two decimal fractions with the same number of digits in the whole part are compared according to the prices of the same floor units in the whole part. For example, $24.45 > 21.78$. Because the number of digits in the integer part and the values of the decimal floor are the same, while the values of the odd floor are different: $4 > 1$.

3. Decimal fractions with equal whole parts are compared according to the number of corresponding floor units in the fractional parts. The number with more decimal floor units is larger: $2.34 > 2.28$. If the floor of decimals is also equal, then the comparison of decimal fractions is hundredths and so on. It is carried out according to the floors. [8; 94]

In the course of the lesson, it is necessary to make students the subjects of such activities that they remember the following and can benefit from them: When zeros are added to the end of the fractional part of a decimal fraction, its value does not change: $14.62 = 14.6200 = 14.62000$; When zeros are removed from the end of the fractional part of the decimal fraction, its value does not change: $113.21000 = 113.2100 = 113.21$; When writing a decimal fraction, move the comma to the right by one, two, three, etc. when shifting the position, the value of the fraction is 10, 100, 1000, etc. times increases. For example, in the decimal fraction 2,671, when the comma is shifted 2 digits to the right, the number 267.1 is obtained. That is, the value of the fraction 2,671 increases 100 times: $2,671 < 267,1$. [7; 80]

When selecting examples of tasks presented to students to form their skills of comparing decimal fractions: 1) Comparison plays an important role in the formation of the student's speech and judgment abilities. Therefore, this reality should be drawn into the center of attention when the assignments are being made; 3) The table of floor units should be used in the comparison of decimal fractions. Students should be sufficiently involved in comparing decimal fractions according to their position on the number line; 4) There

should be a place to express the comparison of decimal fractions with the help of inequality signs; 5) Pupils should be involved in the activity of determining the numbers between two decimal fractions (then pupils understand that hundredths are greater than tenths, thousandths are greater than hundredths), etc. [9; 95]

During the lesson, students' activity and ability to perform tasks are assessed through observation. Pupils' oral explanations, modeling skills, and written works are in focus.

"Rounding of decimals. Approximate sum, approximate difference" sub-topic should be allocated 2 hours. Thanks to the teaching of this topic, students should be able to: 1) round decimal fractions to the required level; 2) solving various problems related to rounding of decimal fractions.

It is recommended to start the lesson by repeating the rounding rule on natural numbers. The teacher notes that rounding decimals is similar to rounding natural numbers. Rounding up to wholes, tenths, and hundredths on examples is done by students' activity. It is clear to the students that it is possible to find the sum and difference approximately by rounding the decimal fractions to the whole number according to the addition and subtraction rule. In this case, the approximate result will differ more than the exact result.

It is recommended to form rounding skills in activities on type tasks [8; 81].

During the lesson, students are evaluated according to their activity and ability to perform tasks. It is possible to apply different tools for the purpose of evaluation. For example, it would not be bad to use tasks like the following: Write 3 decimal fractions equal to 5.7 when rounded (5.69; 5.68; 5.71); Write the smallest decimal fraction that, when rounded, is equal to 5.7; 5.67; Write the largest decimal fraction written using only the numbers 3, 4, 5, 7, and rounded up to 5.7; Round the smallest decimal fraction between 3 and 4 written with only the numbers 2,3,4,5 to hundredths.

It is enough to devote 5 hours to teaching the sub-topic "Addition and subtraction of decimal fractions". Thanks to the teaching of this topic, students should be able to: find the sum and difference by rounding decimal fractions to whole parts (units); resolves issues related to approximate calculations [8; 97]

The teacher explains the addition and subtraction of decimal fractions by modeling on the grid (with the active participation of the students). He first $1.56 + 0.42 = ?$ He performs modeling in his example. According to the number 1.56, one of the 2 hundred squares is completely colored, and 56 cells of the second one are colored. Then 42 more of the remaining cells of the 2 hundredth square are colored according to the sum of 0.42 (it is better that the separated cells according to the sums are colored differently). By counting all the colored cells, it is possible to see that the sum is $1.56 + 0.42 = 1.98$. A subtraction is modeled with a similar approach. For example: $1.35 - 0.48 = ?$

One of the two 100 squares corresponding to the number 1.35 is colored completely, and 35 cells of the other are colored. 48 colored squares corresponding to 0.48 subtracted from the colored cells are crossed out. By counting the remaining cells, see that the difference is $1.35 - 0.48 = 0.87$ can be. [7; 83]

In the further continuation of teaching the subject, the teacher brings to the students' attention that addition and subtraction of decimal fractions are performed in writing as in natural numbers. Addition and subtraction are performed on numbers of floor units. By writing zeros at the end of the fractions with a small number of digits, the number of digits in the fractional parts is equalized and the corresponding actions are performed. This is more important for performing subtraction.

The teacher visualizes the application of the rule based on an example (it is necessary to take advantage of ICT opportunities in this process). One of the important tasks in teaching the subject is to learn that the properties of the addition operation (the properties of transposition and grouping) are also true for fractional numbers. Students should be able to use these properties in their practical activities. Experience shows that the results in teaching the subject are conditioned by the selection of tasks, systematization and the form of organization of students' activities on tasks.

The results of the students' activities on the tasks should be analyzed in the lessons focused on the teaching of the subject, groups should be formed based on this, and appropriate worksheets and repetitions should be determined.

It is enough to allocate 5 hours for the teaching of the subtopic "Multiplication of decimal fractions". As a result of teaching the subject, students should be able to: 1) perform multiplication on decimal fractions; 2) to present the act of multiplication on decimal fractions on floor tables, in models; 3) perform examples and problems related to multiplying decimal fractions by floor units; 4) to use the properties of multiplication during calculations; 5) to solve problems based on the skills of estimating the product.

In the first lesson aimed at teaching the subject, students' attention is focused on multiplying decimal fractions by natural numbers. In that exercise, the procedure for multiplying decimal fractions by natural numbers is explained to the students: 1. Multiplication is performed as in natural numbers without paying attention to the comma; 2. The number of digits after the comma in the result must be equal to the number of digits after the comma in decimal fractions; 3. The numbers are counted from right to left and the whole part is separated from the fractional part with a comma; 4. Decimal fraction to 10, 100, 1000, etc. to multiply, you need to move the comma to the right by the number of zeros (1, 2, 3, etc. number), and if there are no numbers, add zeros. [6; 325]

After this rule explained to students is applied on examples, tasks selected with special competence are presented to groups for execution on worksheets, results are presented and discussed.

The teaching of the topic is carried out as a process of mastering the rule of multiplying decimal fractions by decimal fractions in the next lesson. Multiplication of decimal fractions is modeled according to the number of rows and columns, as in natural numbers. Work $0.5 \cdot 0.9 = ?$ is presented on a specific example: 1) a 10×10 cell grid is drawn. 5 out of 10 lines are separated by a special colored line according to the 0.5 stroke. These cells correspond to the first stroke; 2) According to the number 2.0,9, 9 out of 10 columns are separated by a

line of another color. These cells correspond to the second multiplication; 3) 45 out of 100 cells fall into the common part and this part is separated by coloring. The colored part corresponds to 0.45 part of the grid. $0.5 \cdot 0.9 = 0.45$. [8; 91]

As a continuation of the lesson, the following is brought to the students' attention: When multiplying a decimal fraction by a decimal fraction, the number of digits after the comma in the product must be equal to the sum of the digits after the comma in the multiplication. Decimal fraction 0.1; 0.01; 0.001 and so on. to multiply, you need to move the comma one, two, three, etc. to the left.

The required skills of students regarding multiplying decimal fractions by decimal fractions are formed in the process of performing appropriately selected tasks. The (textual) application of problems related to multiplication of decimal fractions is more useful in this regard. It is recommended that one of the lessons dedicated to the teaching of this subject be focused on the solution of textual problems. It is important to draw students' attention to the concept of "approximate product" related to multiplication of decimal fractions. Students should remember: 1) If the decimal fractions are greater than one, the product can be approximated by rounding the multiplication to the highest place of the whole part ($23.45 \cdot 28.87 \approx 600 \rightarrow 20 \cdot 30 = 600$). 2) If the numbers are less than 1, the product can be approximated by rounding them to tenths ($0.385 \cdot 0.618 \rightarrow 0.4 \cdot 0.6 = 0.24$).

Pupils should be aware of the procedure for writing zero in the floors of the product and should be able to include it in their practical activity when necessary: 1) Multiplication is performed as in natural numbers, without taking into account the comma; 2) The numbers after the comma in the punctuation marks are counted; 3) By writing zeros to the left of the resulting number, the number of digits is completed to this number and a comma is placed. In the process of performing the tasks given by class and groups, students develop the skills of applying the presented rule.

As a result of teaching the subject, students' ability to perform multiplication on decimal fractions and solve problems on decimal fractions is evaluated through observation. The student's presentation of the problem solution is kept in mind.

It should be noted that with the help of websites it is possible to prepare worksheets and use them as a self-assessment tool [12-17].

It is enough to allocate 5 hours for the teaching of the subtopic "Division by decimal fractions and division of decimal fractions". As a result of teaching the subject, students should be able to: 1) Multiply and divide decimal fractions by floor units; 2) Divide whole numbers into decimal fractions; 3) divides a decimal fraction into a decimal fraction; 4) Divides a decimal fraction into a whole number; 5) Solving problems by applying division on decimal fractions.

In scientific-methodical sources, it is recommended to start the first lesson related to the teaching of the subject [8; 108-110]. Examples are written on the board: $4:0$, 2 and $4:2$. Students easily find that the ratio $4:2$ is 2 .

It is recommended that the teacher use modeling to explain the division by decimal fractions in his example, he can suggest modeling with the help of rectangles.

The teacher says: "Let's draw four rectangles and divide each of them into 10 equal parts and divide the parts by two. That is, let's find how many 0.2 are in 4 integers: $4:0.2 = 20$ ($20 \cdot 0.2 = 4$)".

Then students are offered: $8:0.25 = ?$ This means finding how many $1/4$ s are in 8 ($25/100 = 1/4$). 1 integer will be four grains $1/4$, and 8 integers will be $8 \cdot 4 = 32$ grains $1/4$. So, $8:0.25 = 32$ ($32 \cdot 0.25 = 8$).

The first lesson continues with the execution of tasks related to the presentation of the division act with a model.

The topic for the next lesson (a sub-topic of the topic "Division by a decimal fraction") is defined as "Division of a decimal fraction by a natural number". This lesson is built as a pedagogical process related to learning the algorithm of dividing a decimal fraction into a natural number and using this algorithm in practical activities.

The algorithm is presented as follows: 1. As a result of each division step, a number is written on the corresponding floor of the part; 2. The numbers obtained from the division of the whole part are written in the floors of the whole part. 3. The remainder obtained from the full part is added to the floor units of the fractional part and the division process is continued; 4. As a result of each division step corresponding to the fractional part, a number is written on the corresponding floors of the fractional part of the part; 5. To divide a decimal fraction by 10, 100, 1000, you need to shift the comma to the left by the number of zeros (1, 2, 3, etc. number), and if there are not enough numbers, add zeros from the left. [6; 327-329]

The lesson continues with the group execution of tasks related to the division of a decimal fraction into a natural number. The topic for the third lesson (a sub-topic of the topic "Division by Decimal Fractions") is defined as "Division of Decimal Fractions by Decimal Fractions". This lesson is organized as a pedagogical process related to the learning of the algorithm of dividing a decimal fraction into a decimal fraction and using this algorithm in practical activities.

The algorithm is presented as follows: 1. The division of a decimal fraction by a decimal fraction is brought to the division of a decimal fraction by a natural number. 2. Depending on the number of digits of the divisor after the comma, both the divisor and the divisor are divided into 10, 100, 1000, etc. is shot. Thus, the divisor is expressed as a natural number.

The teacher brings to the students' attention the importance of remembering such a rule: Decimal fraction to 0.1, 0.01, 0.001, etc. 1.2 according to the comma to divide. 3 and so on. the number should be shifted to the right, and if there are no numbers, zeros should be added from the right.

The lesson continues with the execution of tasks related to the division of a decimal fraction into a decimal fraction by groups. In the next two exercises, the activities of the students are directed and directed on the textual problems and summarizing tasks related to the division of decimal fractions into decimal fractions.

It is recommended to draw attention to the use of the "whole-part model" in solving problems.

Small summative assessment criteria: 1. Models decimal fractions on a grid of 100; 2. Arrange the decimal fractions according to increasing or decreasing order; 3. It presents the comparison of decimal fractions on the number axis; 4. Decimals are rounded up to the required level; 5. Solves various problems related to rounding of decimal fractions; 6. Finds the approximate sum and difference by rounding the decimal fractions to the whole part (to units); 7. Presents the act of multiplication on decimal fractions on floor tables, with models; 8. Uses properties of multiplication during calculations; 9. Solves problems based on the ability to estimate the result; 10. Multiplies and divides decimal fractions by floor units; 11. Divides whole numbers into decimal fractions; 12. Divides a decimal fraction into a decimal fraction; 13. Solves problems by applying division on decimal fractions. [9; 116]

Conclusion. 1) In the process of teaching the topics covered in the topic "Fractional numbers and actions on them", the focus should be on the selection and application of types of tasks so that students become subjects of verbs based on expected results;

2) In the process of teaching materials on the topic "Fractional numbers and operations on them", the inclusion of necessary terms in the content of the students' active mathematical vocabulary should be considered as an important didactic requirement;

3) It is recommended to use virtual tools (important links for teaching the course) and various worksheets as an additional resource in teaching materials on the topic "Fractional numbers and operations on them";

4) Since the materials (content elements) on the topic "Fractional numbers and operations on them" belong to the "Numbers and operations" content line, in the real pedagogical process both the whole (with the content covered by the subject of Mathematics as a whole) and the parts belonging to each content line (dialectical unity ("system-structure" approach-whole-part relations) between the elements of the subsystems of the other four content lines) should be expected;

5) The expectation of the "opportunity-movement-quality" paradigm in selecting tasks and making them

into a system has a positive effect on the efficiency of the educational process.

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